

DEVELOPMENT PROCESS OF THE LINGUISTICS AS A SCIENCE IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article talks about the role of women scientists in the development of science and innovative development in the new Uzbekistan. Thanks to the President, large-scale work is underway in our country to increase the socio-political activity of women, ensure their rights and interests, create decent working and living conditions, realize their intellectual potential, expand their participation in the public life of society and state-building, and support leadership, organization, and entrepreneurial ability. Due to this, attention is paid to ensuring gender equality in various spheres of our society.

Keywords: test assignments, knowledge assessment, critical thinking, analytical skills, student evaluation, literary education, pedagogical technologies, forms of control, testing methodology, educational standards

In the history of mankind, interest in science gradually develops. With the separation of sciences (mainly philosophy) into a separate type of scientific activity, universal linguistic problems appeared as an interesting subject of study for thinkers. Particularly, the theory of language as an important tool of human communication forms the basis of the research work carried out within the framework of any natural language.

With the intensive intensification of the study of European languages, many orthographic reforms began to be carried out, aimed at comparing letters and sounds.

The concept of J.B. Vico (1668-1744), the author of the work «New Science», occupies an important place in the linguistics of the new era. This work presents a theory about the origin of languages. According to Vico, imitations of sounds first appeared, then exclamation marks, then affixes, and as a result, they gave rise to independent groups of words.

Later, a trend of neo-linguistics arose (in Italy in the 20s of the XX century): according to this trend, language is not a social phenomenon, but an individual phenomenon; there is no single language, but only a dialect-specific isogloss unit. The basis is the discovery of several isoglosses in the Indo-European ancestral language.

At present, the study of culture and language that form the nation, the study of customs, and knowledge of the language as a means of communication are among the main problems requiring study in science. Therefore, the study of the concepts of «language and culture», and «linguoculturology» becomes essential.

Our fellow linguists studied the language system, its stages, and units in linguocultural and pragmatic aspects, namely D.U.Ashurova, Sh.S.Safarov, Sh.Abdinazimov, N.Z. Nasrullaeva, G.Ergasheva, M.Galieva, D.T.Khadjieva, Z.Kh.Uteshova, A.Pirniyazova, N.P.Abdimuratova, G.K.Kdirbaeva, G.A.Usenova and others.

These examples show that women and women scientists contribute to the development of science in our country. Large-scale work is underway in our country to increase the socio-political activity of women, ensure their rights and interests, create decent working and living conditions, realize their intellectual potential, expand their participation in the public life of society and state-building, and support leadership, organization, and entrepreneurial ability. Attention is paid to ensuring gender equality in various spheres of society.

According to historians, at some time there was a dispute about whether a woman is a human being with a soul and spirit similar to a man. Allah Almighty has declared that a woman is in the rank of men from the point of view of mankind. “Whoever does a good deed, male or female, as long as he is a believer, We will give him a pleasant life and reward him with a reward equal to the good (righteous) deeds that he did.”

The value of a person lies in entrusting him with something, making him responsible for an important matter. This is a simple fact of life. This fact underlies the achievement of prestige and career by scientists or officials. The fact that Allah Almighty places on women the same important duty to pray to Himself as on men is the most important evidence that elevates the rank of a woman to the highest.

In order for a woman to find her place both in the family and in the whole society, she must use the opportunities provided to her. Indeed, according to the norms of Islamic Sharia, every woman has equal rights with a man to study, improve her health, increase her wealth, protect her reputation and career, and other human rights. These opportunities are a major factor in their maturation.

In the new Uzbekistan, work to ensure the rights and interests of women, gender equality, and improve working and living conditions have reached a new level. Ratification of the Conventions of the International Labor Organization “On Equal Promotion of Men and Women for Work of Equal Value”, “On Maternity Protection”, “On Discrimination in Employment and Training” is a necessary international measure to protect women’s rights. Rights at the national level - serves as a legal basis.

At the moment, issues related to increasing the prestige and place of women in scientific activities are being addressed - helping scientists to solve social problems in a timely manner, creating organizational opportunities for research, ending the problem of gender discrimination in scientific activities, and establishing prestigious scientific awards for women scientists, research grants, etc. is an effective solution in the further development of this field.

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